

UCSB's 3D imaging and modeling protocol

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ABSTRACT

Three dimensional models of insect specimens offer the potential for a variety of research applications, including taking morphological and trait measurements of insects and automated species identification. Yet high-quality 3d models are challenging to create because of the specimens' small size. Here we overcome this challenge by creating 3d models using focal stacking to take high-resolution images of bee specimens. Sets of 3d images are processed using Zerene Stacker and Photoshop, and the 3d models are created using Agisoft Metashape. Our protocol can be used for both larger insect specimens, like bumble bees and carpenter bees, and small- and medium-sized specimens, such as mason and sweat bees. This protocol is being used by members of the Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration at the University of California, Santa Barbara, and is based on a protocol developed by members of the Big-Bee project.

Protocol Info: Colleen Smith, Sylvia Reyes, Kathryn A Ryan, Mark Smith, Ellie Deer, Evelyn Sanchez, Sheccid Rivas Trasvina, Giar-Ann Kung, Adrian L Carper, Katja C Seltmann . UCSB's 3D imaging and modeling protocol. [protocols.io](https://protocols.io/view/ucsb-39-s-3d-imaging-and-modeling-protocol-c2ubyesn) <https://protocols.io/view/ucsb-39-s-3d-imaging-and-modeling-protocol-c2ubyesn>

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MATERIALS

Camera flash

StackShot

Camera

AC Turbo

Diffusers

Set up the camera system and specimen:

- 1 Turn the camera on. The remote utility used to operate the camera, EOS Utility, will open automatically.

Note

Troubleshooting tip

If EOS Utility is not opening try changing the camera battery, and double check the USB connection between the camera and computer.

- 2 Select the folder icon in EOS Utility.

- 2.1 Go to File Name. Change the start to 0. This ensures photos are saved in the correct order, simplifying organization and post-processing.

- 2.2 Go to the Destination Folder. Set the destination folder to the folder with your name on it, that located is in the Big-Bee-Images folder on the backup hard drive. Do not set the destination folder to be on the main computer because we do not have enough storage space for thousands of photos.
- 3 Make sure both the flash and the camera are being used with AC Turbos instead of regular batteries (i.e., you want to use the batteries that plug into the wall, so that the flash and/or camera don't die on you in the middle of imaging). When using the AC Turbo with the flash, make sure 3 rechargeable batteries are in the flash and one green, false battery.
- 4 We want our 3d images to have a black background, because this makes it easier to mask them. To achieve a black background, the macropod system should be set up facing a cardboard "wall" with black felt pinned to it, as illustrated below. The black felt needs to cover the whole background of the image from corner to corner. Double check with practice photographs.

Photo showing the location of the black felt for our 3d imaging set up.

- 5 If using the macro lens (MP-E 65-mm; for smaller bees), mount the one of the diffusers around the lens. If using the 100-mm lens (for bigger bees like carpenter and bumble bees), do not use a diffuser.

The red arrow points to the diffuser that gets added to the lens.

- 6 Put the bee on the stage mount and secure it with dental wax. If using the 65-mm lens, align the lens at 1x, 2x, or 3x magnification. Record this magnification for later use.
- 7 Turn on the StackShot by pressing down on the power button, located on the top left corner on the side.

Note

Troubleshooting tip:

If you get an error message on the StackShot, hold down on the power button for five seconds to restart.

- 8 Work on positioning the bee. Put the camera in automatic mode for this step. The specimen needs to be tilted approximately 15 degrees from the stand of the stage mount so that the dorsal and ventral sides of the specimen are captured in the images. The specimen also needs to be centered over the hole at the center of the stage, so that all parts of the specimen remain entirely within the image frame when the specimen is rotated.

Example showing bee specimen tilted 15 degrees.

- 8.1 To ensure that the specimen is centered and that it will remain within the frame during the imaging process, rotate the specimen using the Y-axis of the StackShot, and make sure that the bee stays within the image frame the whole time. If the bee starts to go out of the image frame, center the specimen by looking to see which body part of the bee is leaving the image frame. Then very slightly move that part of the bee closer to the center, so that the bee is fully within the image frame. Repeat this process until the bee stays entirely within the image frame and rotate the bee until it is completely centered for the whole 360 degree rotation.
- 9 On EOS Utility, ensure you are using the correct settings:

Camera settings on EOS Utility

9.1 Ensure that the F-stop is set to F8.0.

9.2 The ISO setting will vary depending on the size of the bee and the lens you are using. For small bees with the 65-mm lens, start with an ISO of 500-1000. For big bees with the 100-mm lens, start with an ISO of 5000. As you set up the lighting (step 11), you will take test photos and change the ISO to get a good level of light.

9.3 Make sure your White balance settings are set to Manual Temperature, or K. The color temperature should be set between 4000K to 6000K. Daylight temperature is 5000K so start with that and adjust as needed.

9.4 If your test photos look orange, decrease the color temperature to add blue. If the photos look blue, increase the color temperature to add orange. You can use the color of the background felt to determine if the color temperature is off. In the photos below, a gray felt background was

used. A color temperature of 4700K results in the test photo (middle) with a background that best matches the color of the gray felt.

- 10** Adjust the lighting to minimize glare. Move the flash arms so that the light coming from them is not directly hitting either the camera lens or the specimen. Follow the tips below for minimizing glare depending on what type of lens your using, 65-mm (for smaller bees) or 100-mm (for bigger bees).

Note

65-mm lens

Position the flash arms so that light is coming through the windows of the dome. You can also try draping felt over the area between the dome and the camera lens, to minimize light coming through (see second photo below).

Example of setup for the 65-mm lens.

Example of felt draping over the dome and lens, to help with glare.

Note

100-mm lens

It's harder to get good lighting with this lens, because there's more room for light to hit the specimen. To reduce glare and haloing:

- Angle the flash arms to shine directly up and position the arms parallel to the camera rather than closer to the bee.
- If using a magnification where you can see the dome in the images, remove the dome.
- If wax is in the photo and reflecting light, put black felt over it to reduce glare.

Example of macropod setup for the 100-mm lens.

- 11** Next, take test photos. Before taking any photos, switch the camera from Automatic to Manual mode, and make sure the flash is set to manual mode as well. While taking the test photos, check that the image isn't too bright or too dark, and that there's minimal glare on the specimen. To increase light levels, increase the ISO and/or position the flash arms to be closer to the specimen. To decrease light levels, decrease the ISO and/or position the flash arms to be further from the specimen. See images below for examples of test photos that are too bright, too dark and just right.

Double reminder: only ever take practice photos when both the camera and the flash are set to manual mode. **NEVER** take photos when the camera or flash is set to automatic mode. It can ruin the camera when the AC Turbo is plugged into the flash.

Too dark

Just right

Too bright

12 When you are happy with the lighting, delete all practice photos from your folder.

13 Create a new folder within the date folder that was automatically created by EOS Utility. Name the folder after the catalog number of the bee by scanning the bee’s barcode label, then add “_images” so that your folder has the format catalog#_images (e.g., LACM ENT 602591_images). You’ll put your stacked image files into this folder later. **Don’t skip this step.** It’s important to create this folder now, because it saves the catalog number of the bee, which connects the specimen to the 3d images and 3d model.

Set up the stackshot: x-axis

14 Make sure the StackShot is set to Auto-Distance.

15 Change the step size distance. For the 100-mm lens (used with bigger bees) use a step size of 0.85 mm (850 μ m).

For the 65-mm lens (used with smaller bees) use the depth of field table to below to determine your step size distance in mm, based on the magnification you are using. This table is for an aperture size of F8.

Step sizes by magnification with F8 aperture.

A	B
Magnification	Step size (mm)
1X	0.95
2X	0.36
3X	0.21
4X	0.15

A	B
5X	0.11

16 Select your start point for the x-axis:

16.1 Make sure the StackShot is on the screen for the x-axis (see image below). Using the StackShot, move the focal point of the camera through the specimen until it's **behind** the specimen and the specimen has become completely blurry.

16.2 Rotate the specimen using the y-axis of the StackShot (using the middle of the three vertical lines, see image below). Make sure all parts of the specimen remain blurred and out of focus for the whole 360 degree rotation. If any come into focus, use the x-axis to move the focal point back slightly until the specimen is entirely out of focus again. Once you've rotated 360 degrees without any parts of the specimen coming into focus, set your position as the x-axis start point by selecting Change Start/Stop on the Stackshot and then Set.

Make sure you're on the X screen

Select here to get to the screen (below) where you can rotate the specimen

Select here to get back to the main X screen

Use the Y arrows to rotate the specimen when you're setting the x-axis start and end points

- 17 Next, set the x-axis end point. Using the StackShot, move the focal point through the **front** of the specimen until it is completely out of focus and blurred. Then, rotate across the range of the y-axis, making sure all parts of the specimen remain blurred at all angles. If any parts of the specimen come into focus, move the focal point forward slightly until the specimen is entirely out of focus. Once you've rotated 360 degrees without any parts of the specimen coming into focus, set that position as the x-axis end point by selecting Set.

Set up the stackshot: y-axis

- 18 Move to the y-axis screen by selecting the "X" on the StackShot.

- 19 Make sure the StackShot is set to Mode: Auto-Step.
- 20 Set the number of steps to 140 steps.
- 21 Start with the y-axis at 90 degrees – the 90 degree mark on the rotating stage should line up with the tick mark on the white dome. Select this as your start position. Use the StackShot to rotate the bee 360 degrees until the y-axis is again at the 90 degree mark. Select this as your end position.

Combine axes and start imaging

- 22 Tap through to reach the screen that reads 'Combine X and Y axes.'
- 23 Select "Change Settings" in the lower left corner of the screen.
- 24 The next screen will ask "Does the X-axis step once before moving on, or complete the entire stack?" Select "Complete."
- 25 The next screen will ask "Does the Y-axis step once before moving on, or complete the entire stack?" Select "Step."
- 26 The next screen will ask "Do you want to include the Z-axis?" Select "No."

27 Make sure the camera is in Manual mode.

28

Note

Troubleshooting tips:

If after imaging you notice lots of black or dark photos, this usually means the flash battery is dead or dying. Try replacing the batteries to fix the issue and make sure the AC Turbo is plugged in.

If you get an error message on the camera saying "Full" and/or on EOS Utility saying "No more shots available," this usually means there's no memory left in the place where you're storing your images. To solve this issue, set the destination folder to be on an external hard drive with lots of disk space.

Take a photo of the scale bar and background

29 After all specimen images have been taken, two more photos need to be taken using the exact same camera settings (including magnification) and lighting:

30 Take a photo of the background, which we will later use to mask the specimen

30.1 Name the photo using the format: catalog#_background.tiff (e.g., UCSB-IZC00038960_background.tiff)

31 Take a photo of the pinned scale bar. Make sure the scale bar is completely in focus and is completely parallel to the lens of the camera.

Example photo of pinned scale bar.

31.1 Name the photo using the format: catalog#_scalebar.tiff (e.g., UCSB-IZC00038960_scalebar.tiff)

32

Note

Note: when taking images of the background and scale bar, it is fine to take one photo each. You do not need to take a stacked set of photos for these images.

Batch process and focal stack the images

33 Open FolderAxe and select the folder containing your images.

34 Under "Split Type," select "By Amount."

35 Find the number of images taken in each x-axis stack. This will be the number of steps displayed in the stackshot + 2.

Note

For example, if there are 41 steps in each x-axis stack, you will want a folder for every 43 images.

- 36** Enter this number after “How many files do you want per folder?” Press “Split!”. FolderAxe will then edit the directory inside your folder to create a bunch of smaller folders. You can now close the program.

Note

There should be approximately 140-141 folders. One folder per angle.

- 37** Double check in a few folders (including the last folder) that the images were split correctly. Each folder should contain one set of photos taken of the specimen at the same angle. If you notice a few black or very dark photos, delete these.
- 38** Once the images have been split into folders, stack them using Zerene Stacker. Open Zerene Stacker. Under “Batch,” click “Show Batch Dialog.”
- 39** On the right hand side under “Stacking Tasks”, select your folder and then select “Save in designated folder (with no prefix)”
- 40** Then select “Add,” and select “Align and Stack All (PMax).”
- 41** On the left hand side under “Current Batch” Select all of the folders created by FileAxe (Ctrl+A) and drag them into the Zerene Stacker batch dialog. Click “Save Batch to Queue” on the bottom and then Click “Run all batches.”
- 42** Close the dialogue and wait.

- 43 Once Zerene Stacker has finished stacking, you can delete all folders with the original, non-stacked images in them. Then, empty the trash, so the images don't take up huge amounts of storage space on the computer.

Batch edit in Photoshop

- 44 Open **one** of your focal stacked images in Photoshop
- 45 Navigate to "Window > Actions" and select Actions. A checkmark should appear. This means the Actions tab will show up in the bottom right Layers/Channels/Paths window.

- 46 Create a new Actions folder.

- 47 To record a new action, select the plus button in the bottom right corner of the Actions window. Select "Record"

- 48 The program should start recording automatically. Check that the red "record" button is depressed/darkened.

49 Go to "Image > Adjustments > Curves", or use the shortcut Ctrl+M to open the Curves window.

50 By adjusting points on the diagonal line (the "curve"), you can change the program's thresholds for displaying the darkest and lightest colors registered in the image. You can add additional adjustment points to the curve by clicking on any part of it. Play around until you this tool until you have an image with high contrast between the background and the specimen.

51 Under "Filter > Sharpen > Smart Sharpen", you can use Photoshop's algorithmic sharpening tool to filter out what the program detects as noise and blur. This can help define the edges of the bee and increase the contrast of hairs against the backdrop or make various contrasting parts of the bee more immediately apparent.

Note

If you use this tool too many times or at too high of an intensity, the image may start to look "crunchy," i.e. the program will produce unnaturally high contrast and unwanted digital artifacts.

For reference, here are our settings for this particular bee, which is dark and shiny with very light hairs. It's worth noting that editing for 3D processing may not produce the most aesthetically pleasing image, but one that Agisoft can read well. For a bee with light hair, for example, you will want to refine the edges of the hairs to reduce the “glowing” or “haloing” effect that comes from reflective surfaces. This will improve the automatic masking by making the edges of the bee more apparent.

52 Now that you are done with your edits, press STOP next to the record button to stop recording the action.

53 The photoshopped JPEGS will be placed in a folder labeled “JPEG” in the same folder as the stacked TIFF files.

Model in Agisoft Metashape - Getting started

54 Open Agisoft Metashape Pro.

55 Open Preferences:

For newer versions of Metashape:

Navigate to Preferences by opening “Metashape Pro > Preferences”

For older versions of Metashape:

Navigate to Preferences by opening “Tools > Preferences”

56 Make sure the “Advanced” preferences are set to the following:

57 Make sure the following is added to “Tweaks:” in the bottom left hand corner of “Advanced” settings:

Parameter: BuildModel/ooc_surface_blow_off | Value: 0.9

Parameter: BuildModel/ooc_surface_blow_up | Value: 0.9

Parameter: BuildModel/tv1_mesh | Value: false

- 58 Click "Apply" and "OK."

- 59 Click "Workflow" at the top and select "Add photos."

- 60 Select all the 140 high-resolution photos that have been photoshopped.

- 61 Click "Open" and watch them as they are added to Chunk 1.

Model in Agisoft Metashape - Mask

- 62 Right click on one of the photos and hover over the "Masks" drop down and select "Import Masks..."

- 63 Set "Method" to "From Background."

- 64 Set "Operation" to "Replacement."
- 65 Set "Filename template" to the filename of your background photo. You'll need to type or copy-paste it in.
- 66 The tolerance is by default set to 10. Increase this value if the background is not fully masked out or decrease if the image is masked too much. A tolerance of 29 is the maximum tolerance for good results.
- 67 Masking can be slow for all images, so it's a good idea to test different tolerances on one image first. To test-mask one image Apply to "Selected Images." Navigate to the folder with the background image and select that image. Repeat step 61-66 when testing out different tolerances. Once you are happy with the mask and ready to apply to all images proceed to the next steps.

Example of a well-masked image.

68 Repeat steps 61-66, but apply masks to “All images.”

69 Once all images have been masked, toggle to “Show Masks” (red box on screenshot, below) to have the photos tab on the bottom show you which images have been masked. Double check and make sure everything looks okay.

Note

Sometimes these masks will come out fuzzy, clunky, or inexact, but it’s good to run through the 3d modeling process before returning to manual masking/cleanup. Sometimes, even with poor masks, the model will generate cleanly.

Model in Agisoft Metashape - Align photos

70 Navigate to “Workflow” > “Align Photos” and match the settings to the following.

71 Press "OK" at the bottom and let it run. After this alignment step your model should look something like this:

Model in Agisoft Metashape - Build mesh

72 Navigate to "Workflow" > "Build Mesh" match the settings to the following:

73 Press “OK” at the bottom and let it run. After this build mesh step your model should look something like this:

Model in Agisoft Metashape - Build texture

74 Navigate to “Workflow” > “Build Texture” and match the settings to the following:

Note

In the “Advanced” settings at the bottom, ensure the boxes “Enable Hole Filling” and “Enable ghosting filter” are checked off

75 Press “OK” at the bottom and let it run. After this build texture step your model should look something like this:

76 Once finished, the model is ready to save and export!

Save your model

77 Navigate to "File" > "Save As" and save your file as catalog#_full_model.psx (e.g., LACM ENT 602591_full_model.psx)

78 Save in a folder labeled catalog#_3d (e.g., LACM ENT 602591_3d), that is within the same folder as the stacked photos.

Back up your work

- 79** At the end of every day, backup all your work from that day onto the hard drive called “Second Backup for 3d.” Copy all work from the day onto this hard drive by dragging it into the Big-Bee-Images folder of that hard drive.

General file organization

- 80** **Important.** Before moving on to the next bee, make sure your general file organization is in the right format.

Example of how images and models of a single specimen should be organized in your folder.

catalog#_photoshopped

- JPEG photos of bee that were batch photoshopped
- Photo of background (make sure its photoshopped with the same settings as the bee JPEGs)
- Photo of scale bar (does not need to be photoshopped)
- Photo of bee with scale bar photoshopped on (does not otherwise need to be photoshopped)

catalog#_tiff (e.g., LACM ENT 602591_tiff)

- Raw TIFF files of bee from Zerene stacker
- Photo of background (this will be a JPEG not a TIFF, that's okay)

- Photo of scale bar (this will be a JPEG not a TIFF, that's okay)
- Photo of bee with scale bar photoshopped on (this will be a JPEG not a TIFF, that's okay)

catalog#_model (e.g., LACM ENT 602591_model):

- this will have all your model files from Agisoft Metashape in it.